

Impact of Pesticide Usage in Vegetables its Benefits and Risks

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Abstract:

Pesticide that may remain or in food after they are applied to food crops. The levels of these residues in foods are often stipulated by regulatory bodies in many countries. Exposure of the general population to these residues most commonly occurs through consumption of treated food sources. Many of these chemical residues, especially derivatives of chlorinated pesticide exhibit bioaccumulation which could build up to harmful levels in the body as well as in the environment. Persistent chemicals can be magnified through the food chain and have been detected in the food products. In 1970, DDT was banned for use in agriculture, but it remained a widespread and persistent environment contaminants. Vegetables constitute the vital constituents used in day to day diet and residual toxicity occurs due to over usage of pesticides, which causes health problems among many peoples.

Introduction:

Vegetable crops play a significant role as important source of food and income. Because of the wide adaptability of many existing vegetables, they can also fit into cropping systems. Furthermore, vegetables constitute a major source of income efforts in many small holders, especially near cities (Guan 1990). India has a wide variety of climate and soils on which a range of vegetables crops can be grown. During the last two decades considerable emphasis has been laid on production of these crops in our country, and vegetable have been stepped up (Chadha, 2000). In vegetable production, India is the largest producer next to China with an annual production of 81 million to from 5.12 million ha of land, over the past few years we have realizing the counterproductive effects on health of pesticide use, such as pest resistant to form chemicals (Karanth et al., 1999). Vegetables constitute the vital constituents used in day-to-day diet and residual toxicity occurs due to over usage of pesticides. The need for more vegetables there

became increasingly urgent due to the rapid population growth and the development of a food industry (Sikkhamondhol, 1977). The different kinds of pesticides entire in the market on large scale, and their adverse effects on human beings and environment are also increased. Majority vegetable samples violated and shows persistent nature of different pesticides, mishandling, environmental pollution and presence of pesticide residues (Sheikh et al., 2023).

Result & Discussion:

Indian tropical is generally favorable for the rapid buildup of pests, which often cause serious damage to vegetable crops. Pesticides are widely used the productivity of agricultural commodities and hence are essential component in modern agriculture. The USA, research and extension efforts in developing and implementing IPM on major crops have paid extremely good dividends in terms of crop and environmental protection (Adkisson, 1986). Acute poisoning cases among sprayer groups of farmers in Indonesia

have also been reported increase, specifically for those involved in cultivation (Mustamin, 1988). Although accidental deaths from pesticide poisoning are rare, this does not imply that chronic hazards are non-existent or will continue to remain isolated. Today, highly potent chemicals such as methamidophos are freely used in many parts and the dangers involved given inadequate attention. Even some banned pesticides which have found their way into the vegetable farming areas and being used clandestinely. The directly intake of contaminants depends on both food habitat of the exposed population and concentration in foods. The factors which influenced the concentration of the food are food processing, preparations, seasonal changes, geographical location etc hence, dietary intake has identified as the main route of human exposure to these toxic residues of pesticides. The use of chemicals in modern has significantly increased productivity. But it has also significantly increased the concentration of pesticides in food and in our environment, with associated negative effects on human health. Annually there are dozens of million cases of pesticide poisonings worldwide (Richter,2022). Risk assessment practices also play a role in pesticides regulation. There is a lot of evidence for instance that a significant portion of food samples still exceeds the maximum residue limits set by regulators. Finally, risk perceptions may also influence pesticide regulation. Indeed, there is evidence that people underestimate the risks from natural carcinogens but that they never the less overestimate the risks from carcinogenic pesticides (Slovic2022). The aim of this study is to contribute to the understanding of the health effects of pesticides exposure.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, our health literature review showed that most research focused on individuals

with direct exposure to pesticide, e. g. farmers. Since research on people with indirect exposure was harder to find, and since most individuals belong to this group, more research should be conducted analyzing the potential effects of pesticides on consumers. Some suggestions to the consumers for reducing their potential exposures to toxic chemical contaminants. a) Grow your own vegetables b) Organic vegetables should be purchased c) The vegetables should be washed properly to remove chemicals d) Avoid vegetables with high fat content, and e) Remove peels of vegetables.

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